

Reactions of Ortho-esters of Germanium. Part I. Reactions of Phenol with Germanium Tetrachloride and Tetra-ethoxide

R. C. Mehrotra and G. Chandra

Reactions of phenol with germanium tetrachloride and ethoxide in different stoichiometric ratios have been studied.

The chemistry of ortho-esters of group IV elements has received considerable attention during the last few years. Extensive work has been done in these laboratories on ortho-esters of silicon¹, titanium², and other group IVA³ elements.

A perusal of the literature reveals that very little is known about the similar derivatives of germanium. Preparation of germanium tetraphenoxide was described by treating germanium tetrachloride with phenol in presence of sodium⁴. The method was further extended by Johnson and Fritz⁵ for the preparation of germanium alkoxides. Later, Bradley *et al.*⁶ prepared a number of alkoxides either by passing ammonia into a mixture of germanium tetrachloride and the appropriate alcohol in benzene or by alcohol interchange.

Recently, the preparation of titanium phenoxide and mixed alkyl aryl orthotitanates has been described from these laboratories by treatment of titanium alkoxides with phenol⁷.

In view of the above, it was considered of interest to study the reactions of phenol with germanium tetrachloride and ethoxide in different stoichiometric ratios.

It has been found that phenol reacts with germanium tetrachloride on being refluxed in benzene (I). The reaction is very slow, which is understandable in view of the unreactivity of alcohol with germanium tetrachloride even on refluxing⁷. A similar observation has already been made about the greater reactivity of phenol with titanium tetrachloride², affording titanium tetraphenoxide, whereas the corresponding reaction of alcohols results in the formation of dialkoxide dichloride derivative only¹.

Germanium tetraphenoxide can be conveniently prepared by passing ammonia in a mixture of germanium tetrachloride and phenol (excess) in benzene, hydrogen chloride thus being removed as ammonium chloride (II). The yield in this reaction was, however, poor

1. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 731.
2. Varma and Mehrotra, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 147.
3. Mehrotra, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 904.
4. Schwarz and Reinhardt, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1745.
5. Johnson and Fritz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 718.
6. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4916.
7. Tabern *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2043.

due to a little hydrolysis during extremely slow filtration of ammonium chloride from the reaction mixture.

The reaction between germanium tetraphenoxide and hydrogen chloride gas has also been carried out and germanium tetrachloride has been obtained as the final product (III). It is interesting to mention here that similar reactions of titanium phenoxide² showed the replacement of only one phenoxy group with chlorine (IV).

The reaction between germanium ethoxide and phenol was investigated more thoroughly by causing them to react in predetermined stoichiometric ratios. The four ethoxy groups of germanium ethoxide molecule are successively replaced by the aryl groups in refluxing benzene. The replacement of the last ethoxy group appears, however, to be comparatively much slow. This is probably due to steric hindrance. The mixed ethyl aryl orthogermanates (A to C) can be prepared in quantitative yields by reactions (V) to (VII).

The above reactions were carried out in refluxing benzene and the liberated ethanol was fractionated azeotropically. The products were freed of solvent (C_6H_6) under reduced pressure. The mixed ethyl aryl orthogermanates are colorless monomeric liquids which suffer thermal disproportionation when an attempt is made to distil them under reduced pressure. A gradual increase in viscosity occurs as the number of aryl groups increases in the orthogermanate molecule; finally the phenyl orthogermanate is obtained, which is a colorless viscous liquid (monomeric), b.p. 220-25°/0.3-0.4 mm, miscible with chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, *n*-hexane, and ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable standard ground joints was employed for entire experimentation and the reactions were protected from moisture. Most of the reactions were carried out in semimicro quick-fit assemblies.

Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in *n*-hexane by a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) employing thermistor sensing.

Ethyl orthogermanate was prepared by ammonia method⁶, b.p. 85-86°/12 mm. [Found: Ge, 28.68; OC₂H₅, 70.8. Calc. for Ge(OC₂H₅)₄: Ge, 28.7; OC₂H₅, 71.26%].

n-Hexane was dried (for determining the molecular weights) over sodium and distilled, b.p. 68.4°. Ethanol was first refluxed over freshly ignited quicklime for 6 hours and then distilled. The distillate was redistilled over sodium. Finally it was dehydrated azeotropically with benzene before use, b.p. 78.4°. Phenol (B. D. H., A. R.) was purified by distillation, b.p. 180-82°. Benzene was stored over sodium wire for 2 days, refluxed over sodium metal, and distilled. Finally it was dehydrated azeotropically with ethanol. Ammonia gas was dehydrated by passing through a battery of benzene solution of aluminium isopropoxide and finally through towers packed with aluminium isopropoxide. Germanium tetrachloride (Johnson and Mathey) was used without further purification.

The compounds were moistened with few mls. of aqueous ammonia containing a few drops of ethanol, evaporated to dryness in an electric oven at 80°, and ignited to GeO₂ at 900°. Ethanol in binary azeotropes with benzene was estimated by determining the unchanged chromic acid after a weighed sample of the azeotrope had been kept for two hours with an excess of the reagent (*N*-K₂Cr₂O₇ in 12.5% H₂SO₄).

Phenoxy group was estimated by adding a known amount of bromate-bromide solution to the test solution, acidifying, and titrating the excess of bromine iodometrically.

Germanium Tetraphenoxide. (Pphenyl Orthogermanate).—Germanium tetrachloride (0.94 g.) was refluxed with phenol (4.61 g.) in benzene (10.0 g.) at 100°. After half an hour, HCl gas was detected at the top of the condenser. The refluxing was continued at 110-15° for about 150 hours after which the evolution of HCl gas was found to have become very slow.

The refluxing was stopped and excess of the solvent was removed at the pump. The compound was heated under reduced pressure, when a colorless liquid appeared at 45°/0.1 mm, which readily solidified to a colorless crystalline mass (identified as phenol). Afterwards a colorless viscous liquid (1.5 g.) was obtained, b.p. 210°/0.1 mm. [Found: Ge, 16.31; OC₆H₅, 83.7. Calc. for Ge(OC₆H₅)₄: Ge, 16.33; OC₆H₅, 83.67%].

Germanium Tetraphenoxide (by Ammonia method).—Phenol (7.1 g.) and the tetrachloride (3.88 g.) were dissolved in benzene (100 g.) and dry ammonia was passed in. White clouds of NH₄Cl began to form in the vapour space with very slow formation of ammonium chloride. After a few minutes an exothermic reaction developed with the precipitation of ammonium chloride. A similar phenomenon was observed in the formation of germanium alkyl esters⁶. The supply of ammonia gas was discontinued when the reaction mixture attained the temperature of the room. The ammonium chloride formed was gelatinous and was filtered in a sintered glass funnel. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure when a colorless viscous liquid (2.5 g.), b.p. 220°/0.3 mm, was obtained. [Found: Ge, 16.30; OC₆H₅, 83.8. Calc. for Ge(OC₆H₅)₄: Ge, 16.33; OC₆H₅, 83.67%].

Reaction between Germanium Tetraphenoxide and Hydrogen Chloride.—To a colorless solution of germanium tetraphenoxide (2.12 g.) in benzene (7.5 g.) was bubbled slowly a

current of dry HCl gas for 90 minutes. After about half an hour, noticeable heat was produced. The supply of HCl was discontinued when the reaction mixture had cooled down to room temperature. The colorless solution was refluxed at 95-100° for 3 hours in order to expel the excess HCl gas. The solvent was distilled between 80° and 84°. The last traces of benzene were removed at the pump (40 mm) and the colorless residue obtained was kept for few days from which about 1" long crystals (identified as phenol) separated. The distilled solvent contained Ge and chlorine but no phenol.

Reaction between Ethyl Orthogermanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:1).—Phenol (0.94 g.), ethyl orthogermanate (2.53 g.), and benzene (50.0 g.) were stirred to yield a colorless solution, which was refluxed under the fractionating column at 110° for 2 hours. The ethanol liberated was completely fractionated. The remaining solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the compound dried at 50° at 2 mm for 1½ hours. A colorless liquid (2.94 g.) was obtained. The azeotrope was found to contain 0.47 g. of ethanol against 0.46 g. (calc.). [Found: Ge, 24.2; OC₂H₅, 30.5; M.W., 294.0. (C₆H₅O) Ge (OC₂H₅)₂ requires Ge, 24.15; OC₂H₅, 30.94%; M.W., 300.6].

In an attempt to distil the compound (1.45 g.) two fractions were collected: (i) a colorless liquid (0.62 g.) at 80-83°/9 mm [Found: Ge, 28.7; OC₂H₅, 71.0%. Calc. for Ge(OC₂H₅)₂: Ge, 28.74; OC₂H₅, 71.26%]; (ii) a colorless viscous liquid (few drops) at 204°/0.5 mm containing OC₂H₅, 71.5% [(C₆H₅O)₂Ge (OC₂H₅) requires OC₂H₅, 70.34%].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthogermanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:2).—Ethyl orthogermanate (2.66 g.) was admitted to a solution of phenol (1.98 g.) in benzene (40.0 g.). The solution was refluxed for 2½ hours at 110° and the ethanol liberated was very slowly withdrawn azeotropically till the distillate recorded a temperature of 80.0°. The remaining benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dried at 50° for 2 hours at 1 mm pressure. A colorless viscous liquid was obtained (3.61 g.). The azeotrope contained 0.967 g. ethanol against 0.968 g. (calculated). [Found: Ge, 20.84; OC₂H₅, 53.4; M.W. 349.0. (OC₂H₅)₂Ge(OC₂H₅)₂ requires Ge, 20.82; OC₂H₅, 53.35%; M.W., 348.6].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthogermanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:3).—Phenol (2.51 g.) was treated with ethyl orthogermanate (2.25 g.) in refluxing benzene (35.0 g.) at 110°. The ethanol liberated was fractionated completely over a period of 6½ hours. The ethanol was estimated in all fractions distilling up to 80°. The remaining solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dried at 55° at 0.1 mm for 1½ hours. A whitish viscous liquid (3.45 g.) was obtained. The azeotrope was found to contain 1.20 g. ethanol against 1.229 g. (calc.). [Found: Ge, 18.5; OC₂H₅, 70.6; M.W., 405.0. (OC₂H₅)₃Ge(OC₂H₅) requires Ge, 18.30; OC₂H₅, 70.34%; M.W. 396.6].

In an attempt to distil the above compound (1.46 g.), a few drops collected in the receiver, b.p. 222°/0.3 mm. [Found: Ge, 16.3; OC₂H₅, 83.9%. Calc. for Ge(OC₂H₅)₄: Ge, 16.33; OC₂H₅, 83.67%].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthogermanate and Phenol. (molar ratio 1: excess).—A colorless solution was obtained by stirring together phenol (8.71 g.), ethyl orthogermanate (4.30 g.) and benzene (80.0 g.). It was refluxed under the column at 115-20° for

4 hours. The ethanol liberated in the reaction was carefully fractionated over a period of 12 hours. The remaining solvent and excess of phenol were distilled under reduced pressure. Finally the compound was distilled at 220-25°/0.3-0.4 mm. A colorless viscous liquid (4.8 g.) was obtained. The azeotrope contained 2.95g. ethanol against 3.13g. (calc.) [Found: Ge, 16.30; OC_6H_5 , 83.6; M.W., 436.0. $\text{Ge}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ requires Ge, 16.33; OC_6H_5 , 83.67%; M.W., 444.6].

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF GORAKHPUR,
GORAKHPUR, U.P.

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